

SONET++: A Knowledge Graph of Geographic Categories based on OSM Tag Representation

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Abstract. Semantics of geographic categories are essential for spatial data transfer and data exchange. Different geographic data sources often adopt different natural language terms to describe the same underlying geographic category, and organize these categories with different categorization schemes. As geographic entities and categories are tied intrinsically to space, it is difficult to define a standardized set of geographic categories that are valid across different cultures and languages. In this work, instead of developing a universal ontology for geographic categories, we propose an OSM tag-based semantic representation framework for geographic categories that breaks the semantics of geographic categories into elementary components and describe each semantic component separately using OSM tags. Based on this representation framework, we built a knowledge graph that links thousands of categories from commonly-used geographic data sources (e.g., Wikimapia, Foursquare). This knowledge graph could serve as a foundational information infrastructure that interlinks different data schemas and facilitates the harmonization of heterogeneous crowd-sourced geographic data sources and improve semantic interoperability.

Keywords: geographic category · geospatial semantic · OSM tag · language model.

1 Introduction

Geographic categories are cognitive representations that people use to recognize and categorize geographic entities in geographic reality. A large part of the semantics of data instances is carried by the category that the data instance is assigned to [9]. Geospatial semantics is foundational for integration of heterogeneous spatial data sources, and modeling the semantics of geographic categories is important for semantic interoperability among different geographic data sources [12]. With the rapid growth and wide usage of crowd-sourced geographic information, semantic interoperability becomes even more challenging as the same geographic category is often described by different natural language terms and organized with different categorization schemes. Moreover, geographic entities are intrinsically related to space and categories exist in human mind and

cultures, geographic categorization schemes can be expected to vary in different cultures, languages and disciplines [7], making it difficult to define a standardized set of geographic categories that are valid across different cultures and languages [9].

Developing a universal ontology for geography categories has attracted lots of attention in GIScience research. Previous efforts such as Spatial Data Transfer Standard (SDTS)¹ defined a list of 200 geographic entity types with 244 defined attributes. GeoNames² also developed a list of *feature codes* to categorize different kinds of geographic entities. Different existing categorization schemes usually have to be aligned with each other for the purpose of data exchange. Lots of research efforts have been devoted to ontology alignment, e.g., developing computational models for similarity assessment among geographic categories [1,10], class matching based on contextual embedding model [5].

In this research, instead of developing a universal ontology for geographic categories, we propose an OpenStreetMap(OSM)³ tag-based representation framework for geographic category semantics. Kuhn [6] argued that modeling category semantics should explain the semantics of elementary concepts and provide a mechanism to describe their combinations. Following Kuhn’s theory of category semantic modeling, we break the semantic of geographic categories down into elementary components according to basic formal ontology (BFO) [2]. The semantics of each elementary component is translated into OSM tags and then combined back together. The OSM tag-based representation breaks the original category semantics down into a collection of OSM tags that offers a more granular view of the category semantics. It can serve as an intermediate semantic bridge that interlinks different geographic categorization schemas. We developed a pipeline based on transformer language model [11] and TagInfo API⁴ for mapping geographic categories into OSM tags. With the category translation pipeline, we built a knowledge graph, SONET++, that interlinks over 12,000 categories from commonly-used geographic data sources (e.g., Wikimapia, HERE) through OSM tags.

2 Representation of Geographic Category Semantics

Geographic reality is described in terms of entities and attributes and then captured using digital representations in geographic information systems. Different data sources often categorize and organize geographic entities in different ways. For example, land cover application would include categories such as vegetation, bare land, and water, whereas population modeling would be more interested in the classification of residential, commercial and undeveloped land. In addition, different data sources could use different natural language terms to describe

¹ <https://rosap.nsl.bts.gov/view/dot/4530>

² <https://www.geonames.org/export/codes.html>

³ <https://www.openstreetmap.org/>

⁴ <https://taginfo.openstreetmap.org/taginfo/apidoc>

the same type of geographic entity. For example, Facebook has a *Hotel Resort* category but Google uses *lodging* for this category. These heterogeneities in geographic categories pose significant challenges for achieving semantic interoperability among different spatial data sources.

In upper level ontology BFO, entities are categorized into *continuant* and *occurrent* [2]. In this work, we take a snapshot view of the world and focus on *continuant* or *SNAP entity*, entity that persists or continues to exist through time while maintaining its identity. But it can be extended to incorporate *occurrent* in future work. *SNAP entities* [4] are categorized into *substantial entities* (e.g., lake, building), *SNAP dependent entities* and *spatial region*. *Substantial entities* are enduring entities that are bearers of qualities and are subject to qualitative change. *SNAP dependent entities* consist of *qualities*, *functions*, *roles* etc. of the *substantial entities*.

Categories are grouping of things, and geographic category semantics can vary in many different ways. Geographic categories may describe only *substantial entities* without any semantic attributes, and geographic categories may also just describe *SNAP dependent entities* (e.g., religious place). For instance, *mountain* is a category that only describes a *substantial entity* without any additional semantic attributes, whereas *religious place* describes the function for a place of worship without any enduring entity. *tennis court* category is the combination of a *substantial entity* (i.e., a physical field) and a *SNAP dependent entity* (i.e., the function of the field). Based on the top-level ontology design, the semantics of existing geographic categories can be broken down into individual or the combination of elementary semantic components. Each semantic component is then mapped to OSM tags separately and combined together to form a complete semantic translation of the category. In next section, we will discuss the semantic grouping of OSM keys and how each of the semantic component of a geographic category can be mapped to different groups of OSM tags.

3 Mapping Geographic Categories to OSM Tags

3.1 Represent geographic category semantics using OSM tags

OSM is a widely used crowd-sourced geographic data source that contains a continuously growing number of geographic entities throughout the world. OSM uses a free tagging system to describe geographic features. Geographic features in OSM are described by *tags* that are designed to capture different attributes of the geographic entities (e.g., physical properties, functional affordance). OSM tags, formed by *key=value* pairs, are generated by a large community of users through crowd sourcing. According to OSM tagging schema, *keys* generally specify the type, function, or property of the geographic feature (e.g., *building=**, *amenity=**, *name=**) and *values* provide more details for the *key* (e.g., *building=hotel*, *amenity=restaurant*).

Based on the BFO design discussed in Section 2, we grouped the list of most commonly used OSM keys based on their semantics into *substantial entity keys*

(**SE keys**), *SNAP dependent entity* keys (**SDE keys**) and *spatial region* keys (**SR keys**), respectively (Table 1). The OSM keys listed in Table 1 only show the most frequently used primary keys. Following each primary OSM key, there are also secondary keys that can provide more specific semantics. For example, *natural=** describes various physical geography, geological and landcover features, and *water=** is a more specific key that is combined with *natural=** to describe water body. *cuisine=** is combined with *amenity=restaurant* to describe different kinds of restaurants. According to the design of OSM tagging schema, the **SE keys** only provide physical description of entities and do not imply the current use the entity. Additional **SDE keys** are needed to describe the attributes (e.g., *qualities*, *functions*) of the geographic entity. For example, *building=church* only describes a building that was built as a church, and it does not imply the current function of the building. Note that due to the crowd-sourcing nature of OSM tags, some OSM keys describe both substantial entity and SNAP dependent entity at the same time in OSM database (e.g, *highway=**, *railway=**, *aeroway=**), and they are grouped as SE keys. For example, *freeway* can be translated directly to *highway=motorway*, as *highway=** describes both the physical road entity and the transportation function of the geographic entity, and no additional SDE keys is needed to specify the function.

Table 1. OSM keys for different types of top-level categories

Entity Type	OSM Keys
Substantial Entity	natural=*, building=*, man_made=*
SNAP Dependent Entity	amenity=*, shop=*, industrial=*, tourism=*, leisure=*, healthcare=*, office=*, craft=*, sport=*, military=*, utility=*, public_transport=*
Spatial Region	boundary=*, place=*, landuse=*

After OSM keys were grouped based on BFO types, the semantic components of geographic categories can be mapped to OSM keys in each group separately and then combined back together. Breaking the semantics of geographic categories into elementary semantic components helps in handling geographic category heterogeneities in both textual labels and semantic granularity. As shown in Table 2, both *religious place* and *prayer room* are *SNAP dependent entities* that can be translated to the same OSM tags representation *amenity=place_of_worship*, whereas *anglican church* is broken down into the combination of *SNAP dependent entity* and *substantial entity*. Moreover, the SDE tags for *anglican church* is organized hierarchically from general to specific. The semantic hierarchy among OSM keys allows us to group tags by keys and organize tags hierarchically based on their semantic granularity.

The crowd-sourced OSM tags provide a rich vocabulary for describing semantics of geographic categories and widely-accepted interface with other data

Table 2. Example translation of categories to OSM tags

Category	Data Source	OSM Tags
lake	GeoNames	natural=water, water=lake
congressional district	Facebook	boundary=political,political_division = congressional_district
religious place	HERE	amenity=place_of_worship
prayer room	Foursquare	amenity=place_of_worship
anglican church	Wikimapia	amenity=place_of_worship, religion=christian, denomination=anglican, building=church

schemas, but there are also noises in the tag database. To mitigate this, we follow a set of guiding principles when translating geographic categories into OSM tags:

- Select only the subset of most commonly used OSM tags, i.e., tags that have wiki pages
- When multiple tags have similar meaning (e.g., *building=civic* and *building=public*), tags are selected based on usage frequency from TagInfo API.
- The OSM Tag translation should be as precise as possible. When there are semantic ambiguity, we choose to add more semantics. For example, *church* category does not specify whether the entity is still functioning as a place of worship, and it can be translated as *building=church* or *building=church + amenity=place_of_worship*. We generally choose the latter one.
- Organize the OSM tags based on semantic granularity, from general to specific.

3.2 Category translation pipeline based on transformer and TagInfo API

Based on the representation framework and guiding principles discussed in Section 3.1, we developed a pipeline to translate geographic categories into OSM tags using transformer-based language model and TagInfo API (Figure 1). Transformer based large language models have proven to be powerful in different natural language processing tasks such as language understanding. Bidirectional Encoder Representation from Transformer (BERT) is a pre-trained transformer network [3] that learns the representation of words and sentences and their underlying semantic relations. For commonly-used OSM tags, there is an OSM wiki page explaining the semantic and the intended use of each OSM tag, which are used as input to generate embedding representation for the tag. To generate candidate OSM tags for an input geographic category, we convert the input geographic categories into embedding representation as well and the top ten OSM tags are selected based on the cosine similarity between category embedding and tag embedding.

The candidate tags have to be refined and organized based on TagInfo API because the input category name only provides limited context description. The order and final form of the OSM tags for a category have to be checked and organized by human analyst based on TagInfo API. For a straightforward case like *railway station*, the most similar OSM tag *railway=station* can be directly adopted as the translation result, but for *beach bar* category, the top three candidate tags are *leisure=beach_resort*, *amenity=bar* and *natural=beach*. Human analyst have to check the candidates and then pick *amenity=bar* as the most suitable translation. Then, analysts use **search_tag_combination**⁵ API to retrieve tags that are frequently used together with the selected input tag. For *amenity=bar*, the top five most commonly combined keys/tags are *building=**, *opening_hours=**, *building=yes*, *phone=**, and *website=**. Except for *building=**, the rest are all properties for a specific instance of the category and are not needed to describe the category semantic. Finally, analysts use **search_tag_context**⁶ API to get a list of linked and implied tags of an input tag. After reviewing the returned results of these APIs, we can then set the OSM tag representation for *beach bar* category to be *amenity=bar + bar:type=beach*.

Fig. 1. Pipeline for translating category into OSM tags

Using the transformer and TagInfo API-based translation pipeline, we built a knowledge graph SONET++⁷, an improved version of SONET [8], that linked over 12,000 geographic categories from *Facebook*, *Here*, *Vkontakte*, *Foursquare*, *OSM*, *Wikimapia*, *Google*, *TomTom*, *WRI* and *GeoNames*. The knowledge graph is currently being hosted on a Neo4j graph database server⁸. Users can access and query the knowledge graph through python API interface or Neo4j’s Cypher query language. Users can utilize SONET++ to translate heterogeneous geographic categories into unified OSM tag representation and thus facilitate the conflation of categories from different spatial data sources. When new geographic

⁵ https://taginfo.openstreetmap.org/taginfo/apidoc#api.4_tag_combinations

⁶ https://taginfo.openstreetmap.org/taginfo/apidoc#api.4_tag_wiki_pages

⁷ <https://sonet.ornl.gov/>

⁸ <https://neo4j.haystac-ornl.net:7473/browser/>

categories are discovered, the knowledge graph will be updated with the translation result of the new category.

4 Conclusion

In this work, we proposed a OSM tag-based approach to represent the semantics of geographic categories. The OSM tag-based representation breaks category semantics into elementary components based on BFO ontology and then combine back together. The popularity of OSM tags make it an ideal semantic bridge for interlinking heterogeneous geographic data source schemas. We developed a translation pipeline based on Transformer language model and TagInfo API and built a comprehensive knowledge graph that links over 12,000 geographic categories through OSM tags. This knowledge graph can serve as a foundation to facilitate the conflation of heterogeneous geographic data sources with diverse categorization schemes.

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